

THE STATE OF HEMODYNAMICS IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19 AND CORONARY HEART DISEASE AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF METABOLIC SYNDROME

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Changes in hemodynamics are key links in the pathogenesis of various diseases and conditions [1-3]. Timely correction of pathological abnormalities in the activity of the cardiovascular system contributes to the survival of patients. Adequate monitoring of vital functions is the most important component of critical care medicine [4, 5].

At present, numerous mechanisms of conjugation of the state of microcirculation, macrohemodynamics and heart function, as well as compensatory shifts in microcirculation in response to hypovolemia and impaired cardiac output, have been established [6].

The unfavorable course of a new coronavirus infection is accompanied by significant changes in circulation of blood, the development of shock and multiple organ failure [7, 8]. Concomitant diseases and underlying organ pathology can be crucial for optimizing treatment approaches and speed of recovery [9]. In severe COVID-19, there is a significant increase in hemodynamic indices characterizing low-frequency, high-frequency, and intermediate shifts in the moving blood layer [10, 11]. The degree of hemodynamic disturbance inevitably aggravates the course of many pathophysiological processes, including the severity of intoxication, the course of metabolic processes, as well as the availability of the drugs used to the affected target organs. Timely diagnosis and correction of circulation of blood disorders can have a significant impact on the course and outcome of the pathology. At the same time, so far in the literature we have not found any works that would simultaneously reflect the state of hemodynamics and microcirculation in seriously ill COVID-19 patients depending on the outcome of the disease.

It has been reliably studied that the causative agent of a new coronavirus infection enters the human body through the entrance gate, which is the epithelium of the upper respiratory tract and the epithelial cells of the stomach and intestines. Penetration of SARS-CoV-2 RNA into target cells with type II angiotensin-converting enzyme

(ACE2) receptors is the initial stage of infection. ACE2 receptors are present on the cells of the respiratory tract, especially alveolar cells of type II (AT2) of the lungs, heart, central nervous system, kidneys, bladder, esophagus, ileum, pancreatic parenchyma. Adipose tissue has a high concentration of ACE2 receptors, which facilitates penetration into the cells of the SARSCoV-2 coronavirus [12; 13].

In view of the number of complications with which patients with MS infected with SARS-CoV-2 needed not only hospitalization, but also resuscitation, the problem of MS is even more acute than in the "favorable" period, before the spread of a new coronavirus infection.

Materials and research methods. During the study, 147 people over 18 years of age were examined with a virus infection and all patients were distributed as follows: the main group, which included 59 patients with COVID-19 and CAD on the background of metabolic syndrome; the comparison group, which included 58 patients with COVID-19 and CAD without MS, the control group consisted of 30 healthy individuals without clinical signs of coronary heart disease and metabolic syndrome.

Ischemic heart disease was diagnosed at the prehospital stage by collecting an anamnesis of clinical instrumental laboratory data.

Data are expressed in the following form: mean (M) \pm standard deviation (m). The determination of the interdependence of the considered parameters of the samples using the Student's test and the Pearson chi test (χ^2) was carried out using the test of its significance.

Results. We examined 147 patients hospitalized in the COVID Specialized Center and the Samarkand Regional Infectious Diseases Hospital with a verified diagnosis of COVID-19. Of these, patients with CAD and MS were 59 (30 men and 29 women) and 58 patients with CAD without MS (26 men and 32 women).

To determine the hemodynamic parameters of the heart in patients with COVID-19, we performed a transthoracic echocardiography study 2-3 weeks after the onset of the disease. A comparative analysis of the results of echocardiography in the M-modal mode revealed an increase in the average values of the thickness of the interventricular septum, the size of the left atrium and left ventricle in diastole in the group of patients with COVID-19 and coronary artery disease on the background of MS. The prevalence of structural and functional pathological abnormalities in the main study group significantly exceeded similar indicators in the comparison and

control groups (Table 1). The mean values of the end systolic size of the left ventricle, the aortic root, the amplitude of the opening of the aortic valve and the ejection fraction of the left ventricle in patients with CAD without MS slightly exceeded the established age norms compared with the main group.

According to the results of measurements performed in the B-mode, LV systolic function (EF% according to Simpson, SV ml/m²) in patients with COVID-19 and coronary heart disease against the background of MS were reduced and amounted to 51% compared with similar parameters in the group without MS. The average values of the ejection fraction and stroke volume calculated by the disk method in the main group were 50.93 ± 3.63 and 26.56 ± 2.48 ml/m², in the comparison group 55.54 ± 2.25 and 30.18 ± 1.34 ml/m², respectively. The mean value of LVMI in patients with COVID-19 and coronary artery disease against the background of MS was significantly higher than in the comparison group. The left ventricular SIVR in diastole in both groups corresponded to normal values (<0.45), however, in patients with CAD without MS, it was significantly higher than in the CAD+MS group (Tables 1 and 2).

According to EchoCG data, in patients with CAD against the background of MS, the expansion of the trunk of the pulmonary artery (LA) up to 3.3 cm and its branches up to 2.0 cm is pronounced, and a decrease in the frequency of ejection (47.3-54.56%) and increased pressure in the pulmonary artery (SPPA > 36 mm Hg).

Table 1

M-Modal Echocardiographic parameters in COVID-19 patients with CAD and Healthy Individuals

Index (M ± m)	CAD + MS (n = 59)	CAD (n = 58)	control (n = 30)
Ao, sm	$3,08 \pm 0,15$	$3,04 \pm 0,17$	$3,16 \pm 0,24$
AV, sm	$2,16 \pm 0,05$	$2,17 \pm 0,03$	$2,27 \pm 0,05$
AWRV, sm	$0,57 \pm 0,12$	$0,53 \pm 0,03$	$0,46 \pm 0,05$
ПЗРПЖ, sm	$3,17 \pm 0,03$	$3,14 \pm 0,02$	$3,06 \pm 0,11$
LAD, sm	$3,3 \pm 0,06$	$2,7 \pm 0,02$	$2,01 \pm 0,15$
LAP mm HG	$46,42 \pm 0,52$	$39,15 \pm 0,05$	$31,02 \pm 0,12$
LA, sm	$4,08 \pm 0,15$	$3,56 \pm 0,08$	$3,7 \pm 0,16$
IVS, sm	$1,28 \pm 0,07$	$1,08 \pm 0,07$	$0,94 \pm 0,06$
PWLIV, sm	$1,06 \pm 0,03$	$1,07 \pm 0,06$	$0,97 \pm 0,05$
ESD, sm	$4,22 \pm 0,62$	$4,01 \pm 0,92$	$3,62 \pm 0,14$

EDD, sm	5,85 ± 0,26	5,41 ± 0,19	5,01 ± 0,14
EF, %	50,93 ± 3,63	55,54 ± 2,25	64,82 ± 4,22

Table 2

Parameters of the geometric model of the left ventricle in patients with coronary artery disease

Index ($M \pm m$)	Patients with COVID-19	
	CAD+MS ($n = 59$)	CAD ($n = 58$)
LVMI, g/m^2	118,18 ± 3,78*	102,58 ± 4,28
IRMT of LV	0,41 ± 0,015*	0,39 ± 0,015

1) LVMI - left ventricular myocardial mass index, IRMT- index of relative myocardial thickness in diastole.

2) * - the significance of the difference in indicators when compared with the CAD group at $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 1. Indicators of contractility of the left ventricular myocardium in patients with COVID-19

When determining the type of geometric model of the left ventricle, a significant increase in the number of patients with CAD with $LVMI \geq 118 g/m^2$ and pathological LV remodeling was found in the main study group (Table 3).

Table 3

The prevalence of hypertrophy and pathological deviations of the geometric model of the left ventricle in the study groups

Index ($M \pm m$)	Patients with COVID-19			
	CAD+MS ($n = 59$)		CAD ($n = 58$)	
	absolute value	%	absolute value	%
$LVMI > 118 g/m^2$	29	49**	10	17

LV remodeling (without regard to type)	37	63*	25	43
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* – significance of differences in indicators when compared with the CHD group at $p < 0.05$, ** – at $p < 0.01$.

Normal geometry among patients with COVID-19 and IHD against the background of MS compared with the comparison group was significantly lower (31% versus 12%). In the structure of left ventricular remodeling in patients with COVID-19 and CAD without MS, the concentric type prevailed (55.5% vs. 25%, $p < 0.005$). In patients with COVID-19 and CAD with MS, compared with patients with CAD without MS, concentric LV myocardial hypertrophy was more common (59% versus 10%).

Table 4

The frequency of valvular regurgitation in patients with COVID-19 and coronary artery disease according to the results of Doppler echocardiography

Localization of regurgitation (P ± m)	CAD+MS (n = 59)		CAD (n = 58)		control (n = 30)	
	absolute value	%	absolute value	%	absolute value	%
aortic valve	4	7	5	9	2	7
Pulmonary valve	12	20	8	14	7	23
Mitral valve	32	54*●	18	31	8	27
Tricuspid valve	45	76	37	64	17	57

* – significance of differences in indicators when compared with the CHD group, $p < 0.05$, ● – significance of differences in indicators when compared with the control group at $p < 0.05$.

The proportion of persons with mitral regurgitation among patients of the main study group significantly exceeded their number in the comparison and control groups ($\chi^2 = 6.48$, $p < 0.05$). When analyzing the echocardiographic parameters of the Doppler study, an increase in the flow rate of the period of late filling of the left ventricle and a decrease in the average value of the E/A ratio of the transmitral blood flow in patients with COVID-19 and IHD against the background of MS were found (Table 4).

Table 5

Echocardiographic parameters of right and left ventricular diastolic function in patients with COVID-19 and coronary artery disease

Index ($M \pm m$)	CAD+MS ($n = 59$)	CAD ($n = 58$)	control ($n = 30$)
E_{MV} , m/s	$0,8 \pm 0,02$	$0,84 \pm 0,02$	$0,87 \pm 0,09$
A_{MV} , m/s	$0,79 \pm 0,04$	$0,66 \pm 0,07$	$0,6 \pm 0,09$
E/A_{MV}	$0,96 \pm 0,06$	$1,21 \pm 0,08$	$1,46 \pm 0,07$
E_{TV} , m/s	$0,59 \pm 0,02$	$0,61 \pm 0,04$	$0,62 \pm 0,11$
A_{TV} , m/s	$0,66 \pm 0,06$	$0,63 \pm 0,14$	$0,47 \pm 0,05$
E/A_{TV}	$0,93 \pm 0,06$	$0,96 \pm 0,09$	$1,44 \pm 0,11$

E_{MV} is the maximum flow rate of the early filling period of the left ventricle, A_{MV} is the maximum flow rate of the period of late filling of the left ventricle, E/A_{MV} is the ratio of the early to late filling rate of the left ventricle, E_{TV} - the maximum flow rate of the period of early filling of the right ventricle; $p < 0.05$.

The revealed differences indicate diastolic dysfunction of the LV myocardium in patients with COVID-19 against the background of MS at the initial stage of the development of CAD with a disease duration of 2.25 ± 0.73 years. The analysis of indicators of diastolic function of the right ventricle did not reveal significant intergroup differences, however, the average values of the E / A ratio on the tricuspid valve in two groups were less than 1 and significantly differed from those in the control group (Table 5).

The indicators of diastolic function of the right ventricle were examined in patients with COVID-19 and coronary artery disease against the background of MS (Table 6).

Table 6

The frequency of detection of types of LV myocardial remodeling in patients with COVID-19 with CAD, depending on the presence of MS

	CAD+MS ($n = 59$)		CAD ($n = 58$)		P
Normal geometry	7	12%	18	31%	0.01
Concentric remodeling	15	25%	32	55,5%	0.01
Concentric LVH	35	59%	6	10%	0.002
Eccentric LVH	2	3%	2	3%	0.926

Thus, in patients with COVID-19, a comparative analysis of the results of echocardiographic studies in patients with CAD on the background of MS revealed a significant increase in the thickness of the interventricular septum, the size of the left heart, and the prevalence of left ventricular myocardial hypertrophy. In CAD patients with metabolic syndrome, normal geometry was detected less frequently. In this category of patients, eccentric hypertrophy of the left ventricular myocardium predominated, and a violation of diastolic dysfunction of the left ventricle was also detected.

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